

ASSESSMENT PRACTICES OF PRIMARY STAGE TEACHERS IN ABHA GOVERNORATE IN LIGHT OF THE CORONA PANDEMIC

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to measure the assessment practices employed by primary-stage teachers in the Abha governorate, taking into consideration the impact of the coronavirus pandemic. Additionally, the study aims to measure the significance of statistical inequalities in competence based on years of experience and level of education. The study employed a descriptive research design and utilized a quantitative methodology, wherein the primary data collection tool was a questionnaire, in order to accomplish the objectives of the research. The survey encompassed a population of 287 male teachers from basic education stage schools in the Asir region. Teachers in the Asir region in the basic education stage demonstrated a commendable performance in many metrics of assessment of teachers' techniques, self-assessment techniques, and peer assessment techniques. The results of the study also indicated that there was no significant correlation between demographic variables, such as years of experience or degree of education, and the perspectives of primary school teachers on assessment practices.

Keywords: Assessment Practices, Primary Stage Teachers, Corona Pandemic, Saudi Arabia.

INTRODUCTION

The global dissemination of the Corona pandemic in multiple countries in early 2020 AD had far-reaching consequences that extended beyond the physical harm inflicted upon millions of individuals (Javaid et al., 2023). In addition to the detrimental health effects, various dimensions of economic, social, political, and educational life were profoundly impacted. This was primarily due to the implementation of preventive measures and health protocols by countries grappling with the Corona epidemic (Almossa & Alzahrani, 2022). The educational sector has had significant impact as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic. The suspension of in-person studies in the majority of institutions, as a precautionary step to mitigate the transmission of the virus, posed an unparalleled challenge to the educational standards (Magaji & Ade-Ojo, 2023). The adverse consequences of school closures encompass more than just diminished academic performance, as they also encompass psychological, behavioral, physical, and social harm arising from the lack of the school's educational function (Mäkipää, 2023).

According to UNESCO (2020), the closure of schools, even if it is a temporary measure, incurs significant social and economic consequences. This closure disrupts local communities and disproportionately impacts learners from disadvantaged and marginalized backgrounds (Almeida et al., 2021). Additionally, the closure of schools leads to various adverse effects, including the interruption of learning and disparities in parents' inclination to facilitate remote or home-based education for their children (Wijaya, 2022). The presence of inequality in accessing digital learning platforms and differences in childcare, together with the substantial economic implications, the propensity for

increased school dropout rates, and the social isolation stemming from the absence of schools as a hub for social engagement and interpersonal connections (Ibna Seraj et al.,2022). The level of preparedness of the educational system to address emergency situations has been influenced by various variable elements. The allocation of funding to the education sector, the sophistication of distance education systems, and the level of computer literacy within the local community are significant factors that have influenced the effectiveness of educational systems in responding to the consequences of the pandemic and its impact on educational services (Shibeshi & Baheretibeb, 2023). Additionally, the effectiveness of teacher preparation and qualification programs, along with other less influential factors, have played a crucial role in this regard (Sandvik et al., 2022).

The impact of the epidemic has had significant repercussions for the Saudi educational system. The Saudi Ministry of Education, in its 2020 report, discussed the state of education in the Kingdom in relation to the Corona crisis (Almossa & Alzahrani, 2022). One of the primary challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic is the insufficient funding allocated to the ministry's initiatives aimed at delivering technical, educational, psychological, and social assistance. Additionally, there is a lack of preparedness in terms of curriculum and educational assessment frameworks for emergency scenarios (Almansour & Alaudan, 2022). Insufficient availability of smart devices and computers within schools, coupled with inadequate internet speed, further exacerbates the situation. Moreover, the circumstances surrounding the pandemic have resulted in limited access to the internet and smart devices for a significant number of students (Onyefulu, 2018). The present discourse concerns the interplay of social and economic factors, particularly in relation to the prevalence of high poverty rates and the inadequate allocation of funds towards the production of educational resources for pupils belonging to disadvantaged populations (Monteiro et al., 2021).

In recent years, the global outbreak of the Corona pandemic has led to significant advancements and unprecedented acceleration in various domains, particularly in the realm of education. It has become imperative for nations aspiring to attain a prominent position among their counterparts to prioritize the educational process (Eman et al., 2023). This emphasis ensures the cultivation of an enlightened generation that embodies cultural, moral, and religious values. The preliminary stage of education, also referred to as the basic education stage, is widely recognized as the primary building block upon which subsequent educational stages are constructed (Cahapay, 2020). It is widely recognized that a robust foundation has a favorable impact on subsequent educational stages, while a weak and fragile foundation has a negative impact. Hence, it is imperative to give due consideration to all the fundamental components and facets of the educational process in order to effectively attain the desired objectives (Almansour & Alaudan, 2022). Given the advent of the technological revolution, it has become imperative to prioritize student learning and assess its extent by substituting outdated traditional measurement methods that are no longer capable of keeping up with rapid progress and advancement. Instead, new methods and strategies in educational assessment must be adopted to align

with the evolving educational landscape and attain the desired objectives (Ferretti et al., 2021).

Aligned with the advancement and growth of education, instructional approaches have become more varied and encompass a multitude of research methodologies, investigative techniques, deductive reasoning, and analytical processes (Veugen et al., 2022). Consequently, it became imperative to devise assessment methodologies that align with the emerging instructional approaches. In order to ensure fairness in the assessment of both teachers' performance and students' desired outcomes, it is imperative to strive for justice (Panadero et al., 2022). Educators are faced with the challenge of shifting their focus away from conventional assessment methods in order to effectively evaluate students' progress and accomplishments. This necessitates a concerted effort to develop authentic assessment approaches that align with the fundamental objectives students are expected to attain and demonstrate in their future endeavors (Meccawy et al., 2021).

The significance of enhancing the techniques and mechanisms of educational assessment is in recognizing assessment as an integral component of the educational system. This process allows for the identification of the degree to which the educational system has achieved its desired objectives (Montenegro-Rueda et al., 2021). Additionally, it facilitates the provision of ongoing feedback that aids in the modification and enhancement of the educational system, ultimately leading to increased efficiency and improved quality of its outputs. Educational institutions consistently strive to impart knowledge, attitudes, behaviors, and skills to students through the implementation of curricular policies, study programs, and diverse curricula (Trevisan et al., 2020). Consequently, numerous critiques have been levied against conventional assessment systems that heavily prioritize knowledge quantity in tests while neglecting higher-order cognitive abilities and creative thinking. As a result, teachers and students have experienced heightened pressure and exerted greater effort, leading students to prioritize attaining top grades rather than emphasizing holistic learning and personal growth (Zhang et al., 2021).

Academic consensus among scholars in the field of education is widespread regarding the crucial role and profound influence that instructors exert on the overall effectiveness of the educational system. Educators are commonly acknowledged as the primary human contributors to this system, if not the most crucial ones (Rasyidah et al., 2020). The individual in question undertakes the responsibilities of a leader, guide, facilitator, and influential entity across all domains within the educational system. He is the individual who diligently strives to achieve objectives with a significant level of effectiveness (Chan et al., 2021).

Therefore, it is imperative to underscore the importance of transitioning toward the implementation of a novel form of performance-based assessment in the realm of educational assessment. This approach, commonly referred to as real assessment, encompasses various terms in the education literature, including realistic assessment, alternative assessment, authentic assessment, and others, regardless of their multitude

and diversity (Matar, 2022). The titles are designed to demonstrate the student's accomplishments and assess them in practical contexts, by evaluating their utilization of cognitive abilities such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making. These skills aid in the student's ability to comprehend, evaluate, and appraise knowledge, thereby fostering a commitment to continuous learning throughout their lifetime (Al-Mashaqba & Abu Qwaider, 2020).

Assessment procedures are widely recognized as fundamental components of the overall educational process. The fact that they are widely recognized as imperative and essential, in order to gain a comprehensive understanding of the learner's educational situation, it is crucial to promptly address any shortcomings and deficiencies (Al-Saidi & Al-Shaidi, 2022). This will facilitate a shift in the educational assessment process from a mere regurgitation of information to a practical application that can be effectively assessed. Despite the significance of the matter, empirical evidence indicates that a considerable number of educators continue to employ conventional assessment methods to evaluate student performance (Javaid et al., 2023). Numerous scholarly investigations have corroborated this prevailing trend. There exists notable variability among teachers in the educational domain with regards to the extent of utilization, the assessment methodologies employed, and the assessment techniques and tools employed in their assessment procedures (Magaji & Ade-Ojo, 2023). Therefore, the study aims to identify the assessment practices of primary-stage teachers in the Abha governorate in light of the Corona pandemic.

Research Questions

The objective of this study was to offer answers to the subsequent questions.

1. What is the extent of assessment practices employed by teachers in the basic education level within the Asir region?
2. Are there statistically significant differences in the assessment practices employed by teachers in the basic education level within the Asir region due to the variables of educational level and years of experience?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Assessment is a fundamental aim in analyzing the efficacy of the curriculum within the educational setting, encompassing the learner and the teacher. The three primary areas of emphasis frequently associated with it include enhancing educational benchmarks, refining interpretive methodologies, and producing evaluative assessments (Almosa & Alzahrani, 2022). The process of assessment leads to an increase in student learning levels. The current emphasis on assessment for learning has increased due to its implementation inside the classroom setting, where it serves to evaluate students' level of achievement in relation to learning objectives (Magaji & Ade-Ojo, 2023). Additionally, this form of assessment provides valuable feedback to students, aiding in the development of their learning abilities and the rectification of any shortcomings (Mäkipää, 2023).

Assessment plays a crucial role in daily learning processes as it offers valuable information and indicators for monitoring the efficacy of student learning and evaluating the performance of the educational system. It serves to inform learners about the extent of their progress in academic achievement and mastery of essential techniques and skills (Almeida et al., 2021). Additionally, assessment provides teachers with insights into students' learning progress and their attainment of educational goals and standards. The assessment process focuses on assessing the degree to which students' cognitive, skill, and emotional objectives are met, and subsequently making informed decisions about them (Wijaya, 2022). This process aims to address developmental priorities and promote comprehensive growth by reconfiguring and enhancing the educational setting. Contemporary assessment encompasses a diverse range of strategies and methodologies that ascertain the occurrence of any alterations in pupils' cognitive abilities and proficiencies (Ibna Seraj et al., 2022). What are the factors that contributed to this transformation? Hence, it is imperative to ensure that the assessment process is both ongoing and thorough, encompassing all educational objectives. In the past, the emphasis in educational settings was mostly placed on assessing learning using summative assessment techniques, such as examinations and homework assignments. However, it is now recognized that effective education encompasses a broader scope, encompassing many processes, procedures, and learning outcomes (Shibeshi & Baheretibeb, 2023).

According to Sandvik et al. (2022), the concept of assessment for learning refers to a deliberate and predetermined procedure in which teachers utilize evidence obtained from assessments to adapt their instructional strategies, or alternatively, students and their peers utilize this evidence to modify their own learning approaches. Almosa and Alzahrani (2022), has provided a definition of assessment for learning, which involves the utilization of evidence and dialogue to assess the degree of students' advancement in their learning. This process entails examining the evidence and ascertaining the level to which educational objectives have been accomplished, thereby empowering students with the knowledge of what actions they need to take. In order to enhance, cultivate, and sustain the process of acquiring knowledge. According to Almansour and Alaudan (2022), the purpose of assessment for learning is to augment students' learning, gather significant information and data to facilitate improvement in their academic abilities, and establish supportive strategies that contribute to enhancing their performance. The objective is to assess inputs and implement suitable interventions in order to attain desired objectives and benchmarks. The process of acquiring knowledge and skills.

The characteristics of effective assessment that teachers should prioritize encompass several aspects. Firstly, it should foster classroom discussion, allowing students to engage in meaningful dialogue. Secondly, it should create opportunities for students to learn from one another, promoting a collaborative learning environment. Thirdly, it should be focused on clarifying the necessary steps for students to achieve ongoing success. Additionally, it should provide constructive feedback to students, aiding their continued learning. Lastly, it should encourage students to take responsibility for their own learning, by facilitating effective methods for them to do so (Onyefulu, 2018). Assessment geared

for learning is distinct from conventional assessment methods that primarily serve purposes such as accountability, ranking, or evaluating learner competence. Its primary objective is to enhance student learning. Assessment approaches and procedures exhibit variability, hence accommodating the consideration of individual characteristics and the inclusion of all students in the assessment process (Monteiro et al., 2021).

Assessment for learning encompasses several key principles. Firstly, it involves the ongoing and consistent application of assessment processes throughout the daily learning experience. Additionally, it establishes a connection between assessment processes and the desired learning outcomes and objectives within the domains of mathematics and science (Eman et al., 2023). Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of employing a diverse range of assessment tools and techniques that align with the various activities offered. Moreover, it encourages students to actively engage in self-assessment techniques as a means of assessing their own progress and understanding (Cahapay, 2020). Peer assessment is a pedagogical approach that considers various dimensions of students' learning and fosters the development of their diverse abilities. It acknowledges the individual differences among students and places emphasis on nurturing the talents of those who excel (Almansour & Alaudan, 2022). Additionally, peer assessment is concerned with the implementation of effective assessment techniques and strategies to facilitate learning. Assessment approaches for learning encompass three main categories: teacher assessment techniques, self-assessment techniques, and peer assessment techniques (Ferretti et al., 2021).

Classroom observation is a crucial strategy that relies on the teacher's active observation of students' behavior, work methods, and cognitive growth during the diverse activities conducted inside the classroom setting. The responsibility for implementing these strategies in the classroom setting is with the teacher (Veugen et al., 2022). Due to its beneficial influence on enhancing student learning outcomes and its capacity to effectively address educational challenges identified by teachers through the implementation of assessment for learning strategies. Engage in active learning and foster their cognitive development (Panadero et al., 2022). On a daily basis, educators pose inquiries to their students, actively listen to their responses in order to gain a deeper understanding of their thoughts, closely observe their collaborative efforts, thoroughly analyze their written compositions and visual representations, and facilitate dialogues to encourage active participation and the exchange of ideas (Meccawy et al., 2021). These purposeful and impromptu verbal and written interactions between teachers and students, as well as among students themselves, serve to stimulate students' involvement in the learning process and promote their intellectual growth (Montenegro-Rueda et al., 2021). The individuals are actively involved in a cognitive process of introspection and contemplation over their thoughts, facilitating the identification of a foundational standpoint for future knowledge acquisition that is interconnected with subsequent learning endeavors. Furthermore, it aids educators and learners in assessing the degree of personal and group advancement in the development and enhancement of educational achievements (Trevisan et al., 2020).

Hence, it is imperative to consider a number of principles within the classroom setting to enhance the efficacy of assessment (Zhang et al., 2021). These principles encompass integrating assessment with teaching through meticulous lesson planning, engaging students in assessment processes, offering feedback to both educators and learners, ascertaining students' knowledge gaps, and fostering student motivation and enthusiasm (Zhang et al., 2021). The motivation, preparation, and training of instructors play a crucial role in ensuring the effectiveness of classroom assessment (Rasyidah et al., 2020).

The COVID-19 epidemic has resulted in the interruption of educational activities across all schools, universities, and kindergartens in several parts of Saudi Arabia. Given the far-reaching consequences of the ongoing epidemic, the Ministry of Education has recently declared the implementation of a blended education strategy, which integrates both traditional in-person instruction and remote learning methods (Almosa & Alzahrani, 2022). This announcement was made in reaction to the implementation of physical separation measures within educational institutions.

The Ministry implemented substantial modifications to the educational assessment systems amidst the Corona pandemic (Almansour & Alaudan, 2022). Prior to the issuance of these instructions, there were amendments made due to the fluctuating epidemiological situation in Saudi Arabia. This was a consequence of a considerable number of students opting out of virtual classes (Chan et al., 2021).

The utilization of assessment for learning serves to guide the teaching and learning process in order to effectively address the identified gaps in knowledge and skills. The results obtained from assessment are not solely quantitative data used for making judgments, but rather serve as indicators for the development of students' education (Matar, 2022). These results provide valuable insights into the extent to which learning standards have been attained. The findings of several studies suggest that further research is required to enhance the field of education by investigating the use of assessment strategies for learning lifetime (Al-Mashaqba & Abu Qwaid, 2020). This research aims to evaluate the efficacy of teachers in utilizing these techniques to facilitate students' learning and development (Al-Saidi & Al-Shaidi, 2022). The study conducted by Javaid et al. (2023) has the objective of in order to gather insights from science teachers, supervisors, and parents, this study aims to explore their perspectives on assessment for learning. Specifically, the study focuses on assessing the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of female students.

Additionally, the study aims to propose an improved model for the performance assessment card used for female students, addressing the limitations of the existing cards. The study has employed a descriptive methodology, and the findings of this section have been revealed. The initial phase of the investigation reveals the presence of statistically significant disparities between individuals' beliefs and their attitudes towards assessment for learning, with a notable inclination towards favoring assessment for learning. The provided sample demonstrates support for the ongoing implementation of the continuous assessment system. The use of the suggested approach for assessment for learning demonstrated favorable outcomes in comprehending scientific knowledge,

concepts, and skills, as well as a discernible enhancement. In the realm of social behavioral skills (Veugen et al., 2022).

Previous Studies

Onyefulu (2018) determined. Whether disparities exist in the perspectives of classroom assessment procedures between primary and secondary school teachers in Region One, Jamaica. The study was directed by a set of seven research questions. The research issues were addressed using an analytic survey research approach. The researchers employed a stratified random selection technique to choose a total of 225 teachers. The study involved the participation of a total of 157 school instructors, with 64 teachers from elementary schools and 93 teachers from senior schools. The data were gathered by means of an online survey administered using a web-based questionnaire. The results of the study indicated that educators commonly employed closed-book tests, portfolios, multiple-choice assessments, short answer questions, restricted essays, and fill-in-the-blank exercises as assessment methods. The results additionally indicated notable variations among the educators in their approach to various aspects of assessment. These aspects include organizing test items based on their types, formulating precise instructions for students, providing information about the assessed areas, conducting assessments, grading assessments, elucidating the process of score derivation, allowing students to contest their grades, and utilizing statistical analyses to enhance assessment methodologies.

Almossa and Alzahrani (2022) presented empirical evidence regarding the tactics employed by English language teachers within the setting of higher education in Saudi Arabia. A survey was employed to investigate the present methodologies employed by instructors in the context of classroom evaluation. The study was conducted with a sample size of 287 participants, consisting of 191 women and 94 males. The findings indicated that both male and female participants demonstrated similar levels of appreciation and support for assessments. Nevertheless, it was observed that female participants placed a higher importance on assessment reasons compared to their male counterparts. The item that was least valued among instructors' identified assessment approaches was fairness. Experienced educators who self-identified as proficient in their profession placed a higher level of importance on assessment equity and measurement theory compared to their less experienced counterparts.

Mäkipää (2023) investigated the perspectives of Finnish general upper secondary students about teacher assessment techniques in the context of emergency remote teaching (ERT) for foreign language instruction. The data analysis involved a sample size of 251 students who participated in an online survey. The analysis incorporated both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. The findings indicate that students perceived essays, listening comprehension tests, and self-assessments as the most appropriate instructional activities for ERT, but learning diaries, peer assessments, and portfolios were regarded as less acceptable. Variations were observed in the students' opinions with regards to their prior academic performance. The majority of students conveyed

favorable perspectives regarding the assessment techniques of their language professors in the context of Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT).

Shibeshi and Baheretibeb (2023) the assessment methods of learning outcomes among postgraduate students studying biomedical and pharmaceutical sciences at the College of Health Sciences of Addis Ababa University were examined. A study was undertaken to examine the quantitative aspects of a cross-sectional nature. The study employed structured questionnaires as a means of data collection. The participants of the study were postgraduate students and teaching faculty members who were affiliated with 13 MSc programs in biomedical and pharmaceutical sciences. The study was carried out at the College of Health Sciences of Addis Ababa University. Approximately 300 postgraduates and teaching faculty members were selected using purposive sampling. The data that was gathered encompassed various assessment methodologies, diverse types of test items, and the preferences expressed by students regarding assessment formats. The data underwent analysis through the utilization of quantitative methodologies, including descriptive statistics and parametric testing. The study revealed that several evaluation procedures and test questions were implemented across different disciplines of study without any statistically significant variation. Common assessment styles in educational settings often include regular attendance, oral questioning, quizzes, group and individual projects, seminar presentations, mid-term tests, and final written examinations. Among these formats, short-question and long-question essays are frequently employed as test items. Nevertheless, there was a lack of regular evaluation of pupils' skills and attitudes. According to the students' responses, their predominant preference was for short essay questions, followed by practical-based assessments, long essay questions, and oral examinations.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive design and quantitative approaches to ensure a thorough, precise, and organized presentation of the population's features and data. According to Saunders et al. (2016), descriptive quantitative research aims to characterize or provide a description of the various features of the subject or situation being studied. Thereafter, the collected data is subjected to analysis and thereafter presented.

Population and Sample

A total of 1630 male teachers from elementary schools in the Asir region participated in a study during the second semester of the academic year 2023. According to the data provided by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), a sample size of 320 is deemed enough for representing the population. The main aim of the study was to conduct a comprehensive survey of male teachers in order to ensure that the sample accurately reflected the overall population. Additionally, the study sought to gather a substantial amount of data from the participants and minimize any potential biases in the findings (Blumberg et al., 2014). Consequently, a digital dissemination of the survey was implemented, reaching all teachers. A total of 297 questionnaires were found. According to Hair et al. (2010), a total

of 10 out of the initial 297 surveys were excluded from the analysis due to the presence of more than 50% unanswered questions. A total of 287 questionnaires, which were deemed reliable and valid, were generated as a result of the analysis.

Research Instrument

To achieve the research aims, the researcher sought guidance from prior studies done by Al-Mashaqba and Abu Qwaider (2020) and ALshidi and Alsaïdi (2022) in developing the questionnaire as the research instrument. The survey was partitioned into two distinct sections. The initial component of the survey gathers data pertaining to the participants' "years of experience" and "educational level." Section 2 comprised a total of 25 items designed to evaluate three distinct dimensions of assessment practices. These categories encompass teacher assessment techniques, as represented by items 1-10, self-assessment techniques, as represented by items 11-17, and peer assessment techniques, as represented by items 18-25.

Instrument Validity

A group of ten educational technology specialists from Saudi universities, with expertise in language formulation, scientific accuracy, and clarity, assessed the study instrument to ascertain its validity. According to expert evaluations, all aspects have received approval, albeit with minor linguistic adjustments.

Instrument Reliability

One approach utilized to ascertain the reliability of a measurement entails evaluating the consistency of results by utilizing the same sample and instruments while keeping all other variables constant. The evaluation of response consistency was performed using Cronbach's alpha. According to Saunders et al. (2016), the establishment of a survey's reliability can be determined by its trustworthiness, which is achieved when it attains a score of 60% or higher.

Table 1: Cronbach Alpha Test

Variables	Value
Teacher assessment techniques	0.825
Self-assessment techniques	0.845
Peer assessment techniques	0.811
Total	0.836

The findings presented in Table 1 demonstrate the study's measurements to exhibit a high level of consistency, as seen by their falling within the range of 0.811 to 0.845. Furthermore, each section of the questionnaire yielded a Cronbach's alpha score exceeding 0.60, indicating a high degree of reliability. Consequently, no inconsistencies were observed across the different components of the research instrument.

DATA ANALYSIS

In order to address the research inquiries, statistical analyses were conducted utilizing SPSS software. Specifically, the techniques employed included one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), the independent sample t-test, and the computation of means. According to Cuevas et al. (2004), it is recommended to employ the ANOVA One-Way test instead of the independent sample t-test when comparing the means of three or more groups. Below, we present an elucidation of the findings, ascertained through the utilization of various methodologies employed for their characterization. The item's grade is considered low due to the fact that the mean score is less than or equal to 2.33. The item's grade is classified as moderate, with the mean score falling within the range of 2.34 to 3.67. The item has a high level of quality as indicated by a mean score that is greater than or equal to 3.68.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The descriptive analysis was employed to provide a comprehensive depiction of the profile of the respondents based on their "years of experience and educational qualification." The data reveals that 45.2% of the participants were teachers who had accumulated 6-10 years of professional experience. Additionally, 32.8% of the respondents were teachers who had acquired 1-5 years of experience. Furthermore, 14.3% of the participants reported having more than 10 years of teaching experience, while 7.7% indicated having less than one year of experience. According to the data presented in Table 2, it can be observed that 67.9% of the participants hold a bachelor's degree, while 27.9% have obtained a master's degree. Additionally, a proportion of respondents, specifically 3.7%, possess a higher diploma. A total of 1.1% of the participants possessed a PhD degree.

Table 2: The respondents profile

Variables	Category	N	%
Years of experience	Less than 1 years	22	7.7
	1-5 years	94	32.8
	6-10 years	130	45.2
	More than 10	41	14.3
Educational qualification	Bachelor's	195	67.9
	Higher diploma	9	3.1
	Master	80	27.9
	Phd	3	1.1

The first research question was examined by computing the means and standard deviations for all items related to the extent of assessment practices utilized by teachers at the basic education level within the Asir region.

Table 3: Mean scores and standard deviation

N	Item	Mean	St.dev	Result
	Teacher assessment techniques			
1	Ask closed-ended, specific-answer questions.	4.27	0.75	H
2	Use observation to evaluate students' confidence in their own abilities	4.27	0.68	H
3	Develop thinking skills by asking open-ended questions	4.15	0.78	H
4	Give students enough time to think before raising their hands to answer	3.79	0.85	H
5	Students were given the opportunity to conduct discussions within student groups	4.29	0.70	H
6	Ask students to repeat their classmates' answers in the classroom situation	4.06	0.81	H
7	Students were allowed to evaluate their classmates and provide feedback	3.92	0.80	H
8	Choose the students to answer using name cards	4.30	0.73	H
9	I extract information about students' understanding by drawing pictures and shapes	4.31	0.63	H
10	Ask the students to write their impressions of learning on cards attached to the board	4.14	0.76	H
	Total	4.15	0.57	H
	Self-assessment techniques			
11	Students can determine their ability to respond using face technology	3.87	0.85	H
12	Instruct students to tell their classmates what they learned from the lesson.	4.12	0.75	H
13	Instruct students to tell their classmates about the most incomprehensible thing from the lesson.	4.13	0.75	H
14	Get students interested in telling their classmates about the most useful thing they learned from the lesson	4.18	0.81	H
15	Guide students to determine their ability to respond using the traffic light technique	4.09	0.84	H
16	I help students identify learning lists.	4.16	0.71	H
17	Ask the students to mark the level scale that they think represents their level of learning.	4.14	0.72	H
	Total	4.10	0.60	H
	Peer assessment techniques			
18	Students are asked to evaluate their classmates' responses in the classroom situation.	4.20	0.73	H
19	I help students ask questions to the presenters.	4.28	0.67	H
20	Divide the students into pairs to discuss their ideas.	4.23	0.68	H
21	I direct students to evaluate their classmates' presentations in a classroom situation.	4.10	0.76	H
22	I encourage students to provide feedback on their classmates' presentations.	4.16	0.74	H
23	Instruct students to use self-evaluation scales to evaluate each other's activities.	4.08	0.81	H
24	I use with students self-evaluation lists of things to include in their work to evaluate each other's work.	3.89	0.75	H
25	I apply opinion questionnaires to find out what students think about their classmates' answers.	3.95	0.80	H
	Total	4.11	0.58	H
	Over all	4.12	0.41	H

Based on the data presented in Table 3, the average score for assessment practices was found to be 4.12, with a standard deviation of 0.41. In essence, the educators within the Asir region's basic education stage exhibit a commendable level of proficiency in their evaluation techniques. The teacher assessment technique labeled as "I extract information about students' understanding by drawing pictures and shapes" (item 9) has the highest mean value among all the assessed techniques, with a score of 4.31. The mean score for item 4, which pertains to providing pupils with sufficient time for reflection before responding, is the lowest among all items, with a value of 3.79.

The observed outcome can be attributed to various factors, including the proficiency and expertise of instructors in utilizing peer evaluation methods and self-assessment, the sufficiency of classroom resources, the low student-to-teacher ratio, the extensive curriculum, the light teaching workload, and the inclusion of one curriculum for each instructor. The contemporary nature of the curriculum and assessment framework for education also underscores the necessity for educators to undergo additional training and professional growth in their instructional capabilities. Also, the observed outcome can be attributed to the time-low nature of teacher evaluation procedures, which may implement the school curriculum plan when employed often in the classroom setting. The teacher endeavors to mitigate the educational deficiencies experienced by the students, potentially resulting in an increase in the overall utilization of these instructional strategies. This finding is congruent with Onyefulu (2018), Almosa and Alzahrani (2022), Mäkipää (2023), and Shibeshi and Baheretibeb (2023).

Furthermore, Table 3 presents the average value of 4.10 and a standard deviation of 0.60 for the self-assessment procedures. The aforementioned statement suggests that educators at the elementary education level in the Asir region possess robust self-assessment methodologies. Within the realm of self-assessment approaches, the item that exhibits the greatest mean value is item 8, which pertains to "Encouraging students to share with their peers the most valuable concept they acquired from the lesson." This particular item had a score of 4.18. The test labeled as 11, which pertains to the assessment of students' capacity to utilize facial technology for response, exhibited the lowest average score (3.87) among all the items.

The observed outcome can be attributed to the effect of training and guidance for students from teachers when utilizing self-evaluation techniques. The experience of many teachers in implementing such evaluation methods, owing to their old appointment, may also contribute to the utilization of these techniques. Furthermore, the sufficient time allocated for learning supports teachers in effectively employing these techniques, as the actual class duration exceeds 40 minutes. Consequently, this presents significant support for teachers incorporating these evaluation methods. This finding is congruent with Onyefulu (2018), Almosa and Alzahrani (2022), Mäkipää (2023), and Shibeshi and Baheretibeb (2023).

In addition, the data presented in Table 3 demonstrates that the peer assessment procedures have a mean value of 4.04 and a standard deviation of 0.55. This finding suggests that educators at the elementary education level in the Asir region possess

robust peer assessment methodologies. One of the items within the peer assessment approaches that exhibits the highest mean value is item 19, which states "Programs can be accessed anytime and anywhere," with a score of 4.28. The item denoted as Item 24, which states, "I use with students self-evaluation lists of things to include in their work to evaluate each other's work," obtained the lowest mean score (3.89) among all the items. The observed outcome can be attributed to the expertise of appointed teachers and the adequacy of remote training methods. Also, the implementation of peer assessment techniques has the potential to optimize teachers' utilization of learning time by facilitating the evaluation of daily classroom activities. It is important to note that the effective utilization of peer assessment techniques necessitates ongoing training. In order to foster students' confidence and their capacity to evaluate the performance of their peers, it is imperative to allocate ample time for learning. This allows teachers to effectively implement these techniques. Notably, techniques that necessitate minimal skills and can be executed within a short timeframe are most commonly employed. This finding is congruent with Onyefulu (2018), Almosa and Alzahrani (2022), Mäkipää (2023), and Shibeshi and Baheretibeb (2023).

The second research question was investigated by utilizing the one-way analysis of variance to determine if there were statistically significant differences in the assessment practices employed by teachers at the basic education level within the Asir region. This investigation considered the variables of educational level and years of experience as potential influences.

Table 4: ANOVA

Variable	Gropus	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Years of experience	Between groups	0.270	3	0.051	0.751	0.210
	Within groups	26.210	284	0.101		
	Total	26.48	297			
Educational qualification	Between groups	0.283	3	0.062	0.834	0.340
	Within groups	26.351	284	0.130		
	Total	26.634	297			

Based on the findings shown in Table 4, there is an absence of discrepancies observed across categories in relation to both years of experience and levels of education. The p-values for years of experience and educational qualification, denoted as (0.210) and (0.340) respectively, suggest that there is no statistically significant relationship between these factors and the assessment practices utilized by teachers in the context of basic education.

CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this study was to investigate the assessment practices employed by primary-level educators in the Abha governorate, taking into consideration the impact of the Corona pandemic. The findings of the study revealed that teacher evaluation techniques, self-assessment techniques, and peer assessment techniques were widely utilized by educators at the basic education level in the Asir region. According to the findings, teacher evaluation strategies were found to be the most prominent among the

various assessment approaches, with peer assessment techniques following closely. Conversely, self-assessment techniques were seen to have the lowest ranking. In Saudi Arabia, educators now possess the capability and competence to effectively employ peer evaluation techniques and self-assessment methods. Additionally, they benefit from ample classroom resources, a favorable student-to-teacher ratio, a comprehensive curriculum, a manageable teaching workload, and the implementation of a singular curriculum per instructor. The current curriculum and assessment framework for education highlights the importance of educators receiving more training and engaging in professional development to enhance their instructional abilities.

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References

- 1) Almansour, S., & Alaudan, R. (2022). Saudi EFL Primary School Teachers' and Parents' Perceptions of Online Assessment during COVID-19 Pandemic. *English Language Teaching*, 15(5), 94. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v15n5p94>
- 2) Al-Mashaqba., F., & Abu Qwaid., I. (2020). Evaluation practices for teachers of the first three grades in light of real evaluation strategies. *Journal of the Islamic University for Educational and Psychological Studies*, 28(6).
- 3) Almeida, E., Castillo, D., & Rosero, A. (2021). Assessment practices in some language centers in public Universities of Ecuador and student proficiency outcomes. *Literatura y Lingüística*, (44), 241–262. <https://doi.org/10.29344/0717621x.44.3017>
- 4) Almosa, S. Y., & Alzahrani, S. M. (2022). Assessment practices in Saudi higher education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-021-01025-z>
- 5) Al-Saidi., H., & Al-Shaidi., K. (2022). Mathematics and science teachers' use of assessment techniques for learning in the classroom situation in basic education schools in the Sultanate of Oman. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching Methods*, 1(11), 25-42.
- 6) Blumberg, B., Cooper, D., & Schindler, P. (2014). *EBOOK: Business research methods*. McGraw Hill.
- 7) Cahapay, M. B. (2020). Reshaping Assessment Practices in a Philippine Teacher Education Institution during the Coronavirus Disease 2019 Crisis. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4), Article em0079. <https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/8535>
- 8) Chan, C. K. Y., & Luo, J. (2021). A four-dimensional conceptual framework for student assessment literacy in holistic competency development. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 46(3), 451–466. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2020.1777388>
- 9) Cuevas, A., Febrero, M., & Fraiman, R. (2004). An anova test for functional data. *Computational statistics & data analysis*, 47(1), 111-122.
- 10) Eman, T., Awaiz., A., & Nazirullah. (2023). Assessment Practices and Assessment Skills of Teachers at Secondary School Level: Factorability and Associative Perspective. *Journal of Peace, Development & Communication*, 07(01), 101–116. <https://doi.org/10.36968/jpdc-v07-i01-10>

- 11) Ferretti, F., Santi, G. R. P., Del Zozzo, A., Garzetti, M., & Bolondi, G. (2021). Assessment Practices and Beliefs: Teachers' Perspectives on Assessment during Long Distance Learning. *Education Sciences*, 11(6), 264. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11060264>
- 12) Ibna Seraj, P. M., Chakraborty, R., Mehdi, T., & Roshid, M. M. (2022). A Systematic Review on Pedagogical Trends and Assessment Practices during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Teachers' and Students' Perspectives. *Education Research International*, 2022, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/1534018>
- 13) Javaid, M., Iqbal, M. J., Ishaq, M., & Ul Haq, M. N. (2023). Effect of Assessment Practices on Teaching Contents at Secondary Level. *Winter 2023*, 3(1), 477–488. <https://doi.org/10.54183/jssr.v3i1.173>
- 14) Magaji, A., & Ade-Ojo, G. (2023). Trainee teachers' classroom assessment practices: Towards evaluating trainee teachers' learning experience in a teacher education program. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 7(1), 100467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100467>
- 15) Mäkipää, T. (2023). Students' perceptions of teacher assessment practices in foreign language emergency remote teaching during Covid-19 in Finland. *Studies in language assessment*, 1-25.
- 16) Matar, M. A. (2022). Evaluative practices among basic stage teachers in Gaza in light of the Corona pandemic and the extent to which they achieve the standards of the Joint Network for Education in Emergencies (INEE). *Journal of the Islamic University for Educational and Psychological Studies*, 30(6).
- 17) Meccawy, Z., Meccawy, M., & Alsobhi, A. (2021). Assessment in 'survival mode': student and faculty perceptions of online assessment practices in HE during Covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-021-00083-9>
- 18) Monteiro, V., Mata, L., & Santos, N. N. (2021). Assessment Conceptions and Practices: Perspectives of Primary School Teachers and Students. *Frontiers in Education*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.631185>
- 19) Montenegro-Rueda, M., Luque-de la Rosa, A., Sarasola Sánchez-Serrano, J. L., & Fernández-Cerero, J. (2021). Assessment in Higher Education during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Systematic Review. *Sustainability*, 13(19), 10509. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910509>
- 20) Onyefulu, C. (2018). Assessment Practices of Teachers in Selected Primary and Secondary Schools in Jamaica. *OALib*, 05(12), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1105038>
- 21) Panadero, E., Fraile, J., Pinedo, L., Rodríguez-Hernández, C., & Díez, F. (2022). Changes in classroom assessment practices during emergency remote teaching due to COVID-19. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594x.2022.2067123>
- 22) Rasyidah, U., Triana, N., & Saukah, A. (2020). The Teachers' Assessment Knowledge and Practice: Contribution of the Past-Time Experiences to the Present-Time Decision. *The Qualitative Report*. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2020.4329>
- 23) Sandvik, L. V., Svendsen, B., Strømme, A., Smith, K., Aasmundstad Sommervold, O., & Aarønes Angvik, S. (2022). Assessment during COVID-19: Students and Teachers in Limbo When the Classroom Disappeared. *Educational Assessment*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10627197.2022.2122953>
- 24) Saunders, M, Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2016). *Research Methods for Business Students* (7th edition) Harlow: Pearson.
- 25) Shibeshi, W., & Baheretibeb, Y. (2023). Assessment Practices of Learning Outcomes of Postgraduate Students in Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences at College of Health Sciences at Addis Ababa University: Student and Faculty Perspectives. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, Volume 14, 693–706. <https://doi.org/10.2147/amep.s412755>

- 26) Trevisan, O., De Rossi, M., & Grion, V. (2020). The positive in the tragic: Covid pandemic as an impetus for change in teaching and assessment in higher education. *Research on Education and Media*, 12(1), 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.2478/rem-2020-0008>
- 27) Veugen, M. J., Gulikers, J. T. M., & den Brok, P. (2022). Secondary school teachers' use of online formative assessment during COVID -19 lockdown: Experiences and lessons learned. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12699>
- 28) Wijaya, K. F. (2022). The Utilities of Online Formative Assessment in Indonesian EFL Learning Contexts during Covid-19 Era. *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Learning*, 7(2), 178–198. <https://doi.org/10.18196/ftl.v7i2.14249>
- 29) Zhang, C., Yan, X., & Wang, J. (2021). EFL Teachers' Online Assessment Practices during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Changes and Mediating Factors. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-021-00589-3>